

Convergence in regional well-being in the European Union, 2000 - 2021

Abstract:

The paper examines the changes in well-being across different regions in EU countries from 2000 to 2021. It evaluates a variety of indicators related to material, personal, and community well-being. The results suggest that assuming perfect substitutability among different dimensions can lead to overestimating progress in regional well-being. Additionally, the study finds that the composite regional well-being index worsened from 2000 to 2014 but may have shown signs of improvement from 2014 to 2021. Also, no signs of convergence were found from 2000 to 2014; in contrast, the convergence path might have recovered from 2014 to 2021. However, the methods used to weigh different dimensions led to variations in regional well-being convergence or divergence patterns.

Keywords: Regional well-being, composite index, territorial disparity, convergence, Europe.

1. Introduction

The concept of well-being is a complex and critical aspect of any modern society. Its absence exacerbates income inequality, undermines social stability, and hinders the achievement of social development goals set by most countries. Therefore, the debate on the relevance of well-being is unquestionable. Well-being is a multidimensional concept consisting of both tangible and intangible factors. Efforts to understand how well-being is constructed and in what context to frame it are essential (Decanq et al., 2015).

An individual's well-being can be assessed by examining their quality of life. This can be viewed as a connected set of 'functionings' encompassing states and actions that may be reached, ultimately determining a person's fulfilment. Sen (Sen, 1999) states these functionings are crucial for evaluating well-being. Capabilities are the freedom to do or be what the individual values most. Functionings and capabilities are the central elements of Sen's capability theory. Functionings vary with each person and the different contexts in which people develop. Additionally, well-being can be understood as the harmonious combination of feeling and functioning well, experiencing positive emotions like happiness and satisfaction, nurturing one's potential, maintaining a sense of control over one's life, pursuing meaningful objectives, and fostering positive relationships (Emmerling et al., 2021).

The consensus is that well-being is a multidimensional concept consisting of objective and subjective elements. It not only refers to the assessment of general satisfaction but also focuses on specific aspects of life, such as health, job, social connections, safety and expectations about the future (Emmerling et al., 2021). It is well-accepted that focusing only on income growth as an indicator of individual well-being is rather limited (Hoekstra, 2022, 2020; Decanq & Schokkaert, 2016; Constanza et al., 2016; Durand, 2015; Van der Bergh, 2009; Stiglitz et al., 2009; Stiglitz et al., 2018). Besides the well-known Stiglitz-Sen-Fitoussie (SSF) Report promoted by the Commission on the Measurement of Economic Performance and Social Progress (Stiglitz et al., 2009), these arguments have been continued promoting by various international organisms like OCDE to advancing research on well-being metrics beyond GDP (Stiglitz et al., 2018); and like Wellbeing Research Centre at the University of Oxford (UK) that drives more holistic indicators of well-being (Helliwell et al., 2024).

The OECD defines well-being as a multidimensional construct that encompasses material elements like income, wealth, employment, and housing conditions and non-material elements, such as health status, education, social connections, civic engagement, environmental quality, personal safety, and subjective well-being. This framework emphasizes the significance of measuring essential resources contributing to well-being over time (OECD, 2008, 2014, 2018). Thus, the OECD approach to well-being is undoubtedly relevant in policymaking decisions because it addresses well-being in a systemic and multidimensional way.

Most studies focusing on the analysis of multidimensional well-being have been conducted at the national level. However, there are also efforts at the regional level, with the most prominent being the Human Development Index (HDI) developed by the United Nations Development Programme. This index provides a comprehensive overview of countries and their regions in terms of income, education, and health. Another significant initiative is the EU Social Progress Index (EU-SPI), an alternative to traditional measures based solely on economic indicators. The EU-SPI incorporates twelve components related to social and environmental dimensions, which are further aggregated into three broader dimensions at subnational level.

This paper constructs and estimates the European Regional Well-being Index using data from the Regional Well-Being Dataset published by the OECD. The dataset offers a comprehensive and multidimensional measure of well-being based on nine indicators representing three dimensions of well-being in EU regions. By applying various weighting schemes to these well-being dimensions, different indices are calculated to account for the varying levels of substitution and complementarity among them. Different weighting methods enable the assessment of situations ranging from perfect substitution to a certain degree of complementarity among dimensions, resulting in diverse outcomes.

The empirical evidence obtained in this paper suggests that well-being in European Union (EU) regions is multidimensional, and its progress is relatively lower when the well-being dimensions complement each other. In contrast, when the dimensions are viewed as perfect substitutes, the improvement is more significant, potentially leading to an inaccurate interpretation of well-being. Additionally, there is a correlation between territorial disparity and the level of complementarity among the dimensions of regional well-being, indicating that considering the dimensions as complements leads to increased disparities among EU regions.

When constructing a multidimensional well-being index, there are several limitations to consider. These include variations in the number of dimensions and indicators used and the relative importance of the indicators. The assignment of weights is critical as it influences the trade-off between dimensions and involves making value judgments about what constitutes a good life. This highlights the challenge of selecting an appropriate weighting scheme (Liberati & Resce, 2022; Pinar, 2019; Balestra et al., 2018; Bertin et al., 2018; Decancq & Lugo, 2013).

It is crucial to emphasize that the paper's goal is not to find the best index or weighting schemes but to demonstrate that different weighting schemes lead to significantly different results. The paper presents five types of weighting to illustrate how the allocation of weights to different dimensions can have a greater or lesser impact on regional well-being outcomes.

The paper's primary objective is to analyse the evolution of regional well-being across EU regions from 2000 to 2021 and the convergence patterns using a multidimensional approach. It also seeks to assess the impact of varying weights assigned to different dimensions in constructing a composite regional well-being index. The paper contributes to research on regional convergence using alternative metrics to GDP per capita. This indicator is quite frequent, yet only a few studies analyse convergence from the perspective of alternative well-

being indicators (Peiró-Palomino, 2016, 2019).

Some results that have been obtained indicate that irrespective of the weighting method employed, changes in various well-being dimensions from 2000 to 2021 led to a deterioration in overall well-being. Regional inequality in terms of well-being increased from 2000 to 2014, primarily due to a decline in economic activity, probably resulting from the economic and financial crisis. However, from 2014 to 2018 and from 2018 to 2021, regional well-being improved, and regional well-being inequality decreased. Nonetheless, the behaviour across different well-being dimensions varied noticeably during these periods. The position of regions in the regional well-being ranking varies noticeably according to the aggregation scheme used.

The paper comprises 6 sections, with this introduction being the first. Section 2 provides a comprehensive review of the literature on well-being, examining the critical theoretical and empirical developments that have emerged in recent years. It also discusses the main limitations of using GDP per capita as the prominent macroeconomic indicator of a country's or region's progress. Section 3 outlines the sources of information and methodology used, detailing the dimensions and indicators of well-being employed in constructing the Regional Well-being Index. In section 4, we present the main results, including an analysis of the descriptive statistics of the regional well-being categories, inequality measures, changes over time in the multidimensional regional well-being index and inequality between 2000 and 2021, changes in convergence patterns, and an analysis of the Kernel density functions. The fifth section contains the main conclusions of the paper, along with its main limitations and future lines of research.

The paper provides three key contributions. First, it aims to determine whether regional well-being results are influenced by the weighting method used for different dimensions. Second, it focuses on analysing well-being at a subnational level and its convergence patterns, which is important as there is limited research in these areas. The paper delves into the territorial differences in well-being across EU regions. Finally, it utilizes the latest available OECD Regional Well-being Dataset from 2021 to examine the territorial recovery patterns following the recent health crisis.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Towards a multidimensional concept of well-being

Over the decades, since the Bretton Woods conference, GDP has been the most widely used economic indicator as a measure of well-being. An increase in GDP has been assumed to signify more significant social progress and higher well-being for society. However, GDP per capita as the sole indicator of well-being has been losing credibility over time. Many studies now argue that GDP per capita fails to capture all aspects of well-being and, as a result, suggest new alternatives for measuring well-being beyond a single indicator.

Among the most renowned authors, Sen (1991) and Jasek-Rysdahl (2001), in their essays, emphasise the concept of multidimensional well-being. They argue that well-being cannot be accurately measured solely through economic indicators such as income, purchasing power, or infrastructure. Instead, a comprehensive measurement should consider the subjective perceptions or appreciations of the individual at the time of analysis. They stress that a proper quantitative measurement of well-being should not rely on a single macroeconomic variable, but should incorporate the individual's subjective perceptions and appreciations.

One of the most influential movements advocating for measures beyond GDP per capita as the sole indicator of well-being was the Stiglitz-Sen-Fitoussi (SSF) Commission. This Commission highlighted the limits of GDP as a measure of social progress and proposed alternative measures more suitable for the diverse processes at play. Emphasising the importance of not relying on a single indicator and using all available information (Stiglitz et al. 2009).

The Commission report endorses three subjective dimensions of well-being: 'life satisfaction', 'presence of positive feelings' and 'absence of negative feelings' rather than focusing solely on 'happiness'. The authors state that a multidimensional definition should be used to define well-being, identifying the following key dimensions: material standard of living (including income, consumption, and wealth), health, education, personal activities (including job), political voice and governance, social connections and relationships, environment and safety. Furthermore, they suggest that these dimensions should be considered simultaneously (Stiglitz et al., 2009).

Ever since the SSF Commission, there has been a growing consensus that it is important to develop broad measures of well-being. It has been recognized that policies solely based on GDP per capita may be misguided. Several countries, such as Australia, Ecuador, France, Italy, the Netherlands, New Zealand, Scotland, Sweden, the United Kingdom, and the United Arab Emirates, have advocated for well-being measures and integrated them into the policy-making process (Stiglitz et al., 2018).

Ivaldi et al. (2018) point out several limitations of using GDP as the sole indicator of well-being. First, they argued that GDP only measures purely economic activities, excluding non-market activities such as domestic work, leisure, and charitable activities, which are essential for social well-being. Second, GDP treats all economic activities as positive, without distinguishing between those contributing to well-being and those detracting from it. Third, GDP does not account for the distribution of resources among individuals. Finally, GDP only measures flows of economic activity without considering the environmental and social impacts associated with production.

Another fundamental limitation is that GDP per capita does not consider the distribution and inequality within a country. The argument that all distributional information is irrelevant for evaluating the well-being of individuals in different countries may be valid, but it is not very convincing (Decancq, 2017).

2.2 Examples of standard well-being indices adopted in practice.

So, to address these limitations, various international organisations, such as the United Nations (UN), and the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), have launched initiatives to measure multidimensional well-being using indicators beyond GDP.

The Human Development Index (HDI) was created in 1990 by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) to measure the progress of each country across three dimensions of human development: a long and healthy life, knowledge, and a decent standard of living. In terms of health, it considers life expectancy at birth; for knowledge, it uses a composite indicator including expected years of schooling and mean years of education for adults over 25 years old; and for living standards, it takes into account both labour and non-labour household income, adjusted by international prices (in PPP dollars per capita). The values of HDI can be freely downloaded from 1995 to 2015 at the HDI Database of the Global Data Lab for subnational

analysis¹.

The Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI) developed by Alkire and Foster (2009), marked a significant advancement in the multidimensional approach. It allows for identifying deprivations faced by people in three dimensions: standard of living, education and health, measured using ten indicators. According to the MPI published by UNDP and Oxford Poverty and Human Development Initiative (OPHI), people are considered multidimensionally poor if they experience deprivations in at least three of the ten indicators. This index provides an essential point of comparison with the results based on income poverty lines (Alkire & Apablaza, 2017). The recent MPI data at the subnational level can be downloaded from the Oxford Poverty and Human Development Initiative subnational results MPI 2023².

The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) established the Better Life Index (BLI) initiative to improve well-being metrics and help policymakers make informed decisions (Koronakos et al., 2020). The BLI consists of 11 well-being indicators covering different areas, each representing a crucial aspect of well-being. This tool allows individuals to express their preferences regarding multidimensional well-being and aggregates achievements across the 11 dimensions based on people's individual preferences. The goal is to raise awareness about regional well-being disparities based on people's preferences (Balestra et al., 2018; Mizobuchi, 2014). The most recent regional well-being data is available for 2021 and can be downloaded from the OECD regional well-being website (OECD, 2023)³.

The European Social Progress Index (EU-SPI) measures social progress in European regions, at the NUTS-2 level. It uses 12 components described by a total number of 55 social and environmental indicators, excluding economic aspects. These components are further aggregated into three broader dimensions of social progress: basic human needs, foundations of well-being, and opportunity. The index provides an aggregate score and ranking per country and allows for benchmarking in specific areas of strengths and weaknesses (European Union, 2020). The components include nutrition and primary health care, water and sanitation, housing, personal security, access to basic knowledge, access to information and communications, health and well-being, environmental quality, opportunities, individual rights, personal freedom and choice, tolerance and inclusion, and access to higher education. The index provides information at the regional level, with data available for 2016 and 2020⁴.

Since 2012, the World Happiness Report (WHR) has been assessing individuals' life satisfaction, including well-being indicators, to guide the policy-making process. Indicators beyond GDP, such as social support, life expectancy, freedom, generosity, and the absence of corruption, may explain countries' happiness levels (Helliwell et al., 2024).

Recently, a growing effort has been made to analyse and measure people's well-being at the local and regional levels. This is because well-being is closely linked to health, education, housing, and environmental quality, which primarily influence people within specific local and regional contexts. Local and regional policies are also designed to address and impact these territorial levels. Considering these local contexts when implementing policies can improve the efficiency of interventions and help decision-makers monitor progress, unintended effects, and overall well-being more comprehensively (Olaskoaga-Larrauri et al., 2022).

In this regard, noteworthy studies have been conducted for regions of OECD countries by

¹ <https://globaldatalab.org/shdi/>

² <https://ophi.org.uk/multidimensional-poverty-index/>

³ <https://www.oecdregionalwellbeing.org/>

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/maps/social-progress/2020_en

Liberati & Resce (2022), Dardha & Rogge (2020), Peiró-Palomino (2016, 2019), Dopke et al. (2017), and for EU regions by Calegari et al. (2023), Ferrara et al., (2022), Pinar (2019), Peiró-Palomino et al. (2020), among others. These studies employ multidimensional measures of well-being.

The study by Liberati & Resce (2022) on regional well-being inequalities found that regions' ranking varied depending on the weights assigned to the 11 dimensions making up the BLI. In countries with high heterogeneity in these dimensions, regions could end up at the top or bottom of the well-being ranking based on the chosen weights. Conversely, the results were more consistent in countries with low heterogeneity, with regions tending to stay at the top or bottom of the ranking.

In their 2020 study, Dardha & Rogge (2020) used the OECD Regional Well-being Database and the benefit of the doubt (BoD) method, which involves determining optimal weights to measure the dimensions of multidimensional regional well-being. These dimensions include material living conditions, quality of life, and subjective well-being. They discovered that the results are more consistent in countries with less disparity among regions in these dimensions. Conversely, in countries with a significant difference between the best and worst-performing regions across the three domains, the results are less favourable regarding well-being. Additionally, when accounting for regional differences in factors such as the proportion of the population over 65, the Gini index, and the poverty rates, the regional well-being results correspond with the values of the dimensions, either directly or inversely.

Peiró-Palomino (2016, 2019) used the OECD Regional Well-being Dataset to analyse regional well-being convergence in 395 OECD regions from 2000 to 2014. They used non-parametric techniques and estimated stochastic kernels to observe the distribution and internal mobility over time for the well-being dimensions and aggregate indicators. The study found no evidence of convergence. Instead, it identified two distinct groups of regions with low and high well-being, indicating polarization rather than convergence.

The study conducted by Pinar (2019) is notable for using multidimensional measures of well-being to analyse well-being and inequality in European regions in the years 2000 and 2014. The study used the generalised mean aggregation method with parameter alternation to allow for more interaction between the levels of perfect substitution and complementarity between dimensions in their analyses. When the aggregation is reduced to the arithmetic average aggregation, regions may show clear progress in well-being, masking difficulties in other areas, particularly concerning the well-being of a more immaterial nature). This method implicitly assumes perfect substitution between dimensions of well-being (Decancq & Lugo, 2013). When using a geometric mean for aggregation, the trade-offs between different dimensions of well-being depend on the relative weight and level of achievement among dimensions (Pinar, 2019). Recently, the United Nations adopted this method in developing the HDI, where the worst performers are penalised and cannot compensate for better achievements in other dimensions.

Dopke et al. (2017) analyse data for 2013 at the regional level to measure well-being using the OECD Regional Well-being Index (OECD, 2014b) as an alternative to GDP per capita. The authors noted that determining how to weigh the different dimensions of well-being is a challenge when constructing aggregate well-being indices. They used different analysis methods, including equal weighting of dimensions, factor analysis, and subjective analysis to assess eligibility across regions for European Funds. The authors examine what would happen to the distribution of these funds if a multidimensional well-being index was used instead GDP per capita. Their results showed that using simple averaging methods across dimensions and factor analysis did not significantly change the number of regions funded compared to using

GDP per capita, nor did the exclusion of regions from allocating European funds. Similarly, the exclusion of regions from allocating European funds did not differ much from the traditional approach. In summary, using alternative indices to GDP per capita would only have a negligible effect on the set of regions eligible for the allocation of European funds, as the weights in all index dimensions tended to be similar.

A study conducted by Calegari et al. (2023) suggests examining the Extended Regional Development Index (ERDI) in quintiles integrating three dimensions from the human development index (education, health, and economic conditions) to evaluate the impact of cohesion policy from 2007 to 2013. The study finds that cohesion policy played a crucial role in enhancing regional well-being and individual incomes during times of economic downturn. It also helped narrow the gap between regions, particularly when the addition of Eastern European countries exacerbated disparities.

Ferrara et al. (2022) used an objective indicator to measure the well-being of regions within the EU-15 regions at the NUTS2 level. This indicator comprised five dimensions: economic condition, education, health status, labour market participation, and regional attractiveness. The study also analysed data on regional transfers and found that regional policy in the EU has had varying effects on well-being compared to GDP, depending on the required funding intensities.

In a study by Peiró-Palomino et al. (2019), the impact of governance quality on well-being in 168 European regions was examined using OECD regional well-being data from 2000 and 2014. The study involved creating a multidimensional index comprising ten well-being dimensions using data envelopment analysis (DEA) and multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM). The findings indicated a positive correlation between governance quality and individual well-being, resulting in positive effects on education, employment, income, safety, civic engagement, access to services, housing, and community support.

2.3 The selection and aggregation of well-being dimensions and weighting schemes

Despite the promotion of initiatives to create multidimensional indices for measuring human development, poverty, social progress, and well-being, little attention has been given to the importance of the aggregation methods used in their development. An exception to this is the Human Development Index (HDI), which recently transitioned from using an arithmetic mean to a geometric mean for aggregating dimensions.

The assignment of weights is crucial in the construction of a multidimensional index of well-being, as it influences the trade-off between dimensions and involves making value judgments about what constitutes a good life. As we commented in the previous sub-section, this underscores the difficulty of choosing a suitable weighting scheme (Liberati & Resce, 2022; Pinar, 2019; Balestra et al., 2018; Bertin et al., 2018; Decancq & Lugo, 2013).

Decancq and Lugo (2013) provide a beneficial discussion about the role of these weights and a critical survey of eight approaches to classify them into three categories: the data-driven, the normative, and the hybrid. As the authors point out, the ultimate test of the choice of aggregation method should be whether the trade-off between dimensions is reasonable. Without a widely accepted theoretical framework for the aggregation method, robustness and sensitivity tests should also be established, and cautious interpretations should be made.

Recently, simulations from a large number of vectors of weights have been used in constructing multidimensional regional well-being indices for OECD regions to reflect all the possible

preferences and needs (Liberati & Resce, 2022).

2.4 Regional convergence in GDP per capita versus composite regional well-being indices

The GDP per capita is frequently used in the EU regional convergence analysis as set out in the large existing literature and the recent research of Pina & Sicari (2021), Pintera (2024), and Jankiewicz (2024), among others. It is also traditionally used to analyse convergence developed in the Economic, Social, and Territorial Cohesion Reports (European Commission, 2024). Yet, only a few studies analyse convergence from the perspective of alternative well-being indicators.

Some of the few studies that analyse regional convergence across OECD regions based on composite well-being indicators instead of focusing on convergence in terms of income or GDP per capita are those developed by Peiró-Palomino (2016, 2019). Therefore, further analysis of regional convergence based on composite well-being indicators beyond GDP is needed to improve the effectiveness of regional policies in the EU. In short, from theoretical background and previous research, the primary research questions that will be addressed in this paper are:

- How can different aggregation methods impact the results of EU regional well-being and the robustness of convergence/divergence estimations?
- How has the economic downturn affected EU regional well-being outcomes based on the chosen aggregation method?
- Which EU regions have improved or worsened regarding well-being based on the chosen aggregation method?

This study contributes to the existing literature that advises measuring and analysing the well-being of individuals, regions, and countries using a multidimensional approach and composite indices. It emphasises that if regional well-being is measured with simple indicators, regional policies will be poorly designed, and no progress will be made in improving people's quality of life. The analysis of regional well-being convergence addressed in this paper adds to the debate on regional convergence that has traditionally developed based on regional GDP per capita.

3. Data and methodology

3.1. Dimensions and categories of well-being.

To create the multidimensional regional index, we use the OECD Regional Well-being Dataset for 2000, 2014, 2018, and 2021. Nine dimensions of OECD Regional Well-being have been utilized to assess the advancement of well-being in the EU regions across three categories stated by Pinar (2019): material well-being, personal well-being, and community well-being). These three categories offer a solid foundation for thoroughly analysing different aspects of well-being established in Sen's capabilities approach. The material well-being category brings together the dimensions of income, jobs, and housing, which aligns with the material conditions category in the methodology of OCDE. The quality-of-life category, stated by OCDE, has been disaggregated into two different categories as in the study of Pinar (2019): personal well-being -with education, health, and access to services dimensions- and community well-being – with civic engagement, environmental quality, and safety. However, it might be subjective for the

researcher to allocate specific indicators to one or more of these three categories⁵.

Material well-being includes income, measured by the average household disposable income per capita; jobs, measured by the employment and unemployment rate; and housing, which captures the number of available rooms per unit. Personal well-being covers education, which is measured by the proportion of the labour force with at least secondary education; health, measured as life expectancy and mortality rate; and access to services, calculated as the proportion of households with broadband internet connection. The community well-being includes civic engagement, estimated by voter turnout, environmental quality, evaluated by air pollution levels, and safety, determined by homicide rates.

Table 1 outlines categories, dimensions, and well-being indicators, along with how each indicator is measured. This paper will consider the well-being achievements of EU regions in the years 2000, 2014, 2018, and 2021 to assess the evolution of regional well-being. Data for 2014, 2018, and 2021 include two additional dimensions within the subjective well-being category - perceived social network support and self-assessment of life satisfaction. However, these extra dimensions will be excluded from the analysis as data for 2000 are unavailable, making it impossible to examine their evolution.

Table 1. Categories and dimensions of well-being

<i>Material well-being</i>		
1. Incomes	1.1 Average household income per capita	USD PPP 2010
2. Jobs	2.1. Employment rate 2.2. Unemployment rate	Ratio of employed to working age population Ratio of unemployed to working-age population
3. Housing	3.1 Number of rooms per capita	Number of rooms per capita
<i>Personal well-being</i>		
4. Education	4.1 Labor force with at least secondary education	% Labor force with at least secondary education
5. Health	5.1 Life expectancy 5.2 Mortality rate	Number of years expected to live Age-specific mortality rate of a region
6. Services access	6.1 Broadband access	% Households with broadband
<i>Community well-being</i>		
7. Civic engagement	7.1 Electoral participation	Proportion of voters and number of persons eligible to vote

⁵ As noted by the anonymous referee, the indicators of the dimension of the job can be considered proxies for income generation and not a direct dimension of material well-being.

8. Environmental Quality	8.1 Pollution exposure	PM2.5-weighted average for each region
9. Safety	9.1 Homicide rate per 100,000 inhabitants.	Number of homicides registered per 100,000 inhabitants.

Source: Own elaboration based on OECD Regional Well-being Dataset.

3.2 Methodology and database.

Data on EU regional well-being has been sourced from the OECD's Regional Well-being Database. Information has been collected for 188 regions within 21 EU countries, spanning 2000, 2014, 2018, and 2021 (refer to Table 4 and 5 in the Appendix). As different indicators are measured in various units, they have been normalised for aggregation. The Max-Min method proposed by the OECD (OECD 2008) is used to make comparisons between regions over time. The formula used for the indicators with direct relation is:

$$z_{ij}^t = \left(\frac{x_{ij}^t - \min(x_j)}{\max(x_j) - \min(x_j)} \right)$$

And for the indicators with inverse relation is:

$$z_{ij}^t = \left(\frac{\max(x_j) - x_{ij}^t}{\max(x_j) - \min(x_j)} \right)$$

Where z_{ij}^t y x_{ij}^t are the normalised and actual outcomes in region i for a given indicator j at a given time t , respectively, $\max(x_j)$ y $\min(x_j)$ represent the maximum and minimum value for a given indicator j during the comparison period. It should be noticed that higher normalised values represent higher levels of regional well-being.

It should be noted that this procedure yields normalised annual values of the indicators, but their comparability is limited over the periods analysed. Olaskoaga-Larrauri et al. (2022) suggests normalising the 96th and 4th percentiles instead of the maximum and minimum values to solve this longitudinal comparability.

3.3 Aggregation methods.

In the case of two dimensions (jobs and health dimensions) that include several indicators, there is a two-staged aggregation process. The aggregation within a dimension operates by constructing an average normalized index of each dimension. In contrast, the aggregation across the nine dimensions operates according to each of the five following schemes of aggregation.

The method of aggregation chosen in this paper is the normative type. This method establishes the weight of dimensions according to expert judgment by assigning a fixed number of points among the selected dimensions. It allows regional well-being gains to be assessed based on the complementarity or substitutability between regional well-being dimensions. From a normative or economic policy point of view, if there is no real progress in a person's well-being unless manifested in a broad set of dimensions, we assert that the dimensions of well-being are complementary to each other, and the index should be calculated following this principle.

Conversely, if we consider that well-being can result from progress in one dimension almost exclusively, even at the expense of progress in others, we are admitting a certain substitutability. This would imply the construction of different indices.

Following Decancq and Lugo (2013), we adopt a flexible well-being index formulation as:

$$I(x) = \begin{cases} [w_1 I_1(x_1)^\beta + \dots + w_m I_m(x_m)^\beta]^{1/\beta} & \text{para } \beta \neq 0 \\ I_1(x_1)^{w_1} * \dots * I_m(x_m)^{w_m} & \text{para } \beta = 0 \end{cases}$$

The well-being index is defined as a weighted mean of order β of the transformed outcomes $I_j(x_j)$. The dimension-weights w_1, \dots, w_m are all non-negative and assumed to sum to one.

Thus, parameter β is directly related to the elasticity of substitution σ . Where,

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{1 - \beta}$$

The smaller the value of β is, the less substitutability is allowed between dimensions. According to Pinar (2019) when $\beta = 1$, the elasticity of substitution between transformed achievements is infinite, and the dimensions are considered perfect substitutes. This means aggregation is reduced to simple arithmetic mean aggregation, also known as weighted arithmetic mean. This primarily consists of assigning the exact weighting to the dimensions considered, assuming perfect substitution between dimensions. In this scenario, a lower achievement in one dimension can be compensated by a higher achievement in another.

While this form of aggregation provides a single standardized score for comparison, it does not allow for the identification of the most critical dimensions for overall well-being. Additionally, the assumption of perfect substitution between dimensions is controversial, as research suggests there may be less substitution or some level of complementarity between dimensions.

The second option involves using the geometric mean method of aggregation, also known as the Cobb-Douglas utility function with a β value of 0. In this case, the trade-offs between dimensions depend on the dimension's relative weight and level of achievement. This means that an increase in different dimensions can balance a reduction in one dimension. However, this method penalizes regions with unbalanced achievements in the well-being dimensions, reflecting some complementarity between the dimensions rather than perfect substitutability.

Another possible alternative is to allow β to oscillate between the values of $-\infty$ and $+\infty$, where the elasticity of substitution becomes 0, and the well-being index becomes its minimum or maximum. In this extreme case, substitution between the dimensions is impossible. Therefore, as the parameter β decreases, it becomes more difficult to compensate for a decrease in one dimension with another. The third option involves the harmonic mean, where the parameter β takes the value -1. Changes in dimensions other than the worst-achieved dimension do not affect the composite regional well-being index. Therefore, this method requires regions to promote a perfectly balanced achievement across the dimensions of well-being.

The fourth and fifth proposed aggregation methods involve applying different weighting schemes to all regions. The *most favourable weighting* system involves selecting a scheme for each region that maximises the value of the top two dimensions. In comparison, *the less favorable method* involves maximizing the value of the two worst dimensions. Each region has

its weighting system, and dimensions with higher or lower values must be prioritized. For a given scenario with i regions and j dimensions of regional well-being, the optimization problem for region i can be expressed as follows:

$$\max I_x = \max_{w_{ij}} \sum_{j=1}^j w_{ij} x_{ij}$$

Subject to:

$$\sum_{j=1}^j w_{ij} = 1 \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, n$$

With a weighting system with nine dimensions of regional well-being:

$$\frac{3}{12} \leq w_{ij} \leq \frac{1}{12} \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, n$$

4. Results

4.1 Results of the multidimensional regional well-being index and inequality analysis 2000-2021

Table 2 provides descriptive statistics of the nine dimensions and three categories of the composite regional well-being index for 2000 and 2021. The outcomes of composite regional well-being index have been estimated considering five schemes of weighting based on different values of β parameter: $\beta = 1$ (arithmetic mean) (WBI_1), $\beta = 0$ (geometric mean) (WBI_2), $\beta = -1$ (harmonic mean) (WBI_3), and considering two additional schemes of weighing, the most favourable weighting (WBI_4) and the less favourable weighting (WBI_5).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of dimensions and categories of composite regional well-being index, 2000 y 2021.

Dimensions	2000					2021			
	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max.
Incomes	188	0.58	0.18	0.19	1.00	0.59	0.12	0.34	1.00
Jobs	188	0.67	0.17	0.16	1.00	0.75	0.15	0.32	1.00
Housing	188	0.74	0.18	0.43	1.00	0.75	0.15	0.48	1.00
Education	188	0.72	0.18	0.18	1.00	0.82	0.12	0.46	1.00
Access to services	188	0.57	0.22	0.15	1.00	0.90	0.05	0.75	1.00
Health	188	0.63	0.16	0.12	0.89	0.69	0.08	0.44	0.80
Civic commitment	188	0.60	0.20	0.12	1.00	0.76	0.12	0.40	1.00
Environmental quality	188	0.59	0.18	0.12	1.00	0.57	0.15	0.17	1.00
Safety	188	0.88	0.12	0.28	1.00	0.86	0.09	0.25	1.00
Material well-being ($\beta = 1$)	188	0.66	0.14	0.34	0.91	0.69	0.11	0.44	0.88
Material well-being ($\beta = 0$)	188	0.65	0.15	0.29	0.91	0.68	0.11	0.43	0.88
Material well-being ($\beta = -1$)	188	0.64	0.15	0.25	0.91	0.67	0.11	0.42	0.88
Personal well-being ($\beta = 1$)	188	0.65	0.11	0.38	0.89	0.80	0.05	0.50	0.89
Personal well-being ($\beta = 0$)	188	0.63	0.13	0.33	0.88	0.79	0.06	0.50	0.88
Personal well-being ($\beta = -1$)	188	0.61	0.15	0.25	0.88	0.78	0.06	0.50	0.88
Community well-being ($\beta = 1$)	188	0.69	0.11	0.34	0.90	0.73	0.08	0.53	1.00

Community well-being ($\beta = 0$)	188	0.66	0.13	0.27	0.90	0.71	0.09	0.45	1.00
Community well-being ($\beta = -1$)	188	0.63	0.15	0.21	0.90	0.70	0.11	0.35	1.00
Well-being Index 1 (WBI_1)	188	0.67	0.09	0.47	0.84	0.74	0.06	0.61	0.86
Well-being Index 2 (WBI_2)	188	0.64	0.11	0.41	0.83	0.73	0.07	0.58	0.86
Well-being Index 3 (WBI_3)	188	0.60	0.13	0.34	0.82	0.71	0.08	0.52	0.85
Well-being Index 4 (WBI_4)	188	0.73	0.10	0.51	0.94	0.85	0.07	0.57	0.97
Well-being Index 5 (WBI_5)	188	0.71	0.10	0.48	0.93	0.83	0.07	0.54	0.96

Source: Own elaboration based on OECD Regional Well-being Dataset.

In 2021, the average achievement levels of EU regions are highest in access to services, safety, and education, while achievement levels in jobs, housing, and civic commitment follow closely. In contrast, average achievement levels in environmental quality, incomes, and health are the lowest. Comparing the progress between 2000 and 2021, most dimensions of composite regional well-being have shown improvement, except for environmental quality and safety. The most significant progress has been made in access to services and civic commitment. However, regardless of the value of the β parameter, the highest achievements in well-being are obtained in the personal well-being category, followed by community well-being and, finally, in material well-being.

When these dimensions are combined to calculate the composite regional well-being indices, specific achievement patterns in the average values can be observed. First, when using the arithmetic mean ($\beta = 1$) weighting method, the average values of material, personal, and community categories, as well as the composite regional well-being index (WBI_1) are higher compared to the cases where the achieved values are obtained when the parameter β is less than or equal to zero. In other words, as the parameter β value increases, the average achievement of the three categories of the composite regional well-being index and the mean value of the index also increases.

Each weighting scheme implicitly assigns the relevance of each dimension. Thus, in the aggregation method through arithmetic mean, the importance of each dimension is similar, and the dimensions can be considered substitutes. In the case of the geometric mean, the result is obtained from a joint product of the dimensions raised to the inverse of the number of dimensions. In other words, all dimensions are related to each other; they are complementary, so they are multiplied. Thus, lower values in some dimensions will weigh down the result of the product.

The harmonic mean is calculated as the reciprocal of the arithmetic mean of the reciprocals. It is calculated as the total number of dimensions divided by the sum of the reciprocals. It is a robust measure in the presence of high extreme values. On the other hand, the smaller the value of each dimension or the closer it is to zero, the higher the value of its reciprocal, so that it will have much more weight in the value of the harmonic mean.

This result suggests that if decision-makers prioritize an aggregation method in which substitutability between dimensions is dominant, it will be easier to modify the outcome regarding well-being by compensating for dimensions with lower average achievement to obtain a higher level of regional well-being, which may lead to imbalances among dimensions. On the other hand, if policymakers consider the dimensions of regional well-being as complements, a much more balanced achievement is promoted. For example, when $\beta = 0$ and $\beta = -1$, the mean values of categories of material, personal, community, and regional composite well-being index performance scores (WBI_2 and WBI_3) will be lower than in the cases where

the dimensions are considered perfect substitutes for each other (i.e. the case where $\beta = 1$).

Overall, the average composite regional well-being index tends to be lower when the dimensions are seen as somewhat complementary compared to when they are considered perfect substitutes. Conversely, higher values of the regional composite well-being index are obtained when both the most favourable and least favourable aggregation methods are taken into account.

Figure 1 reports different average composite regional well-being. Regardless of the weighting method, the values of the regional composite well-being index, decreased from 2000 to 2014 due to severe economic and financial crises. After that, regional composite well-being index values recover in 2018 and 2021. Moreover, for all years, the highest values of the composite regional index were obtained with the most favourable weighting method (WBI_4) in 2021, and the lowest values were obtained with the harmonic mean aggregation method in 2014 (WBI_3).

Overall, a conservative approach to the weighting scheme would be advisable. Those that consider a certain degree of complementarity correspond to those methods where $\beta = 0$ and $\beta = -1$. This approach would allow policymakers to shift towards more balanced achievements in all well-being dimensions and consider interventions in those dimensions with the worst results.

Figure 1. Evolution of composite regional well-being index 2000, 2014, 2018, and 2021 using different weighting systems

Source: Own elaboration based on OECD Regional Well-being Dataset.

It’s worth noting that changes are registered, according to the aggregation schemes used to obtain composite indices, when ranking the composite regional well-being index. For instance, Table 6 in the appendix presents the top-15 regions that have obtained higher positions in the composite regional well-being index in 2021. Thus, Drente and Flemish Region (Vlaams Gewest) rank at 3rd and 6th positions based on their overall well-being achievement when the dimensions are considered to be perfect substitutes ($\beta=1$). In contrast, these two regions would have been ranked at the 5th and 12th positions when the dimensions seem alike complements ($\beta=0$), and the 8th and 17th positions when the achievement of dimensions is uneven ($\beta=-1$). On the other hand, Schleswig-Holstein and Baden-Württemberg rank at 3rd and 6th positions (when $\beta=-1$), respectively, 3rd and 9th positions (when $\beta=0$), respectively, and 9th and 14th positions, respectively, when $\beta=1$.

4.2 Convergence in composite regional well-being index levels in EU 2000-2021.

Table 3 provides the average value of three indicators of territorial disparities of the composite regional well-being index: the variation coefficient, the Gini coefficient, and the Theil index for the years 2000, 2014, 2018, and 2021 based on different considerations of β -parameters values used in the construction of the composite regional well-being index.

Table 3. Composite regional well-being index, territorial disparities, 2000-2024-2018-2021

	Variation Coefficient	Gini Coefficient	Theil Index
WBI_1			
2000	0.14	0.08	0.01
2014	0.16	0.09	0.01
2018	0.12	0.07	0.01
2021	0.08	0.05	0.00
WBI_2			
2000	0.17	0.10	0.02
2014	0.20	0.11	0.02
2018	0.15	0.09	0.01
2021	0.10	0.05	0.00
WBI_3			
2000	0.22	0.12	0.02
2014	0.25	0.14	0.03
2018	0.20	0.11	0.02
2021	0.11	0.06	0.01
WBI_4			
2000	0.13	0.08	0.01
2014	0.16	0.09	0.01
2018	0.12	0.07	0.01
2021	0.08	0.04	0.00
WBI_5			
2000	0.14	0.08	0.01
2014	0.17	0.09	0.01
2018	0.13	0.07	0.01
2021	0.08	0.05	0.00

Source: Own elaboration based on OECD Regional Well-being Dataset.

The well-being territorial disparities indicators consistently increased between 2000-2014, regardless of the parameter β used. This can be primarily attributed to the profound impact of the 2008 economic crisis on the European economy, particularly evident in the employment rate, which ended up impacting household welfare. However, there was a positive trend in convergence between 2014-2018 and 2018-2021, leading to a relative decrease in territorial disparities. This improvement occurred as the EU regions successfully recovered from the economic crisis and demonstrated resilience in the face of the recent health crisis.

It is important to note that for the three indicators of territorial disparity, the average value is

higher when considering the dimensions of the regional well-being index as complementary (geometric and harmonic mean) rather than as substitutes (arithmetic mean). This is because using these weights seeks, an equal distribution of achievements across dimensions.

The choice of weighting method used in creating a composite regional well-being index directly affects the resulting average regional well-being index value and the progress (or setbacks) in addressing regional disparities. When dimensions are considered substitutes, the average regional well-being achievement is higher than methods that consider a certain level of complementarity among dimensions. In terms of regional disparities, methods that consider dimensions as substitutes show lower disparities compared to those that consider dimensions as complementary, which exhibit higher values. This penalises the latter for unbalanced progress in achieving goals for overall well-being.

The graphs in Figure 2 show the average levels of territorial disparity indicators in material, personal, and community categories of regional well-being. Looking at the material dimension, we see a similar trend to Figure 1, with convergence worsening in 2014 and improving in 2018 and 2021, regardless of the β parameter. However, in the personal well-being category, we see a sustained improvement in convergence patterns over time, regardless of the β parameter. When it comes to the community well-being category, using the harmonic mean, there is a progressive deterioration in convergence patterns in 2014 and even in 2018, but this seems reversed in 2021.

Figure 2. Territorial disparities of regional Well-being Index by dimensions, 2000-2014-2018-2021

Source: Own elaboration based on OECD Regional Well-being Dataset.

To check the robustness of the composite regional well-being index results in terms of the characteristics and the dynamics of the distribution functions, results of Gaussian kernel densities for the composite regional well-being index using a different scheme of weights are provided. Figure 5 in the Appendix illustrates that kernel density functions for each of the years analysed differ according to the method of aggregating dimensions of regional well-being. When the geometric or harmonic mean is used, average values of the composite regional well-being index are lower than those obtained with the arithmetic mean, but in all cases, they result in unimodal functions. On the other hand, the most favourable (WBI_4) and least favourable (WBI_5) aggregation methods produce bimodal kernel density functions with values concentrated at lower levels than those obtained with the arithmetic mean.

When considering each aggregation scheme separately, the evolution of distribution functions from 2000 to 2021 indicates a convergence process regarding regional well-being at work for EU regions, regardless of the aggregation scheme used (Figure 3). Frequencies around the mean significantly increased during these years, although the distributions in 2021 show signs of polarisation with any of the aggregation schemes used. Additionally, the estimation shows an evolution from a unimodal distribution in 2000 to a bimodal distribution from 2014 onwards, when more and less favourable aggregations are used. Regarding arithmetic, geometric, and harmonic mean, bimodal distribution in 2000 has become more pronounced over time.

Figure 3. Kernel estimation of regional well-being index density function, using different weighting schemes

Source: Own elaboration based on OECD Regional Well-being Dataset.

One of the most used indicators in convergence analysis is β -convergence (Barro and Sala-i-Martin, 1992). β -convergence happens when the relationship between the initial positions and their change over a certain period is negative. In simple terms, there is β -convergence when areas that were in a worse position at the beginning show more improvement over the period compared to those that started from better positions, and vice versa.

Figure 4. Patterns of β - convergence of composite regional well-being index, 2000-2021, 2000-2014 and 2014-2021

4.a.2000 - 2021

4.b.2000-2014

Source: Own elaboration based on OECD Regional Well-being Dataset.

Figure 4.a shows signs of convergence in composite regional well-being index levels of the EU regions from 2000 to 2021, regardless of the aggregation scheme used. There is a negative and significant correlation between the regional well-being index values of each region in 2000 and its changes from 2000 to 2021, evidencing that at this period, EU regions have tended to become more similar regarding the well-being of their inhabitants. Conversely, from 2000 to 2014 (Figure 4.b), results show signs of divergence, at least in the cases of composite regional well-being index values estimated with geometric and harmonic aggregation schemes. For the last period from 2014 to 2021 (Figure 4.c), the convergence pattern in terms of regional well-being in EU regions has been recorded, nonetheless, the aggregation scheme is used. These findings are consistent with the results obtained with the variation coefficient, Gini coefficient, and Theil index.

5. Conclusions.

This paper has studied the evolution of well-being outcomes in 188 regions in 21 EU countries for the years 2000, 2014, 2018, and 2021 and their patterns of convergence. Numerous studies have been carried out on regional convergence in terms of GDP per capita, but only some studies analyse convergence in terms of regional well-being.

The use of the multidimensional approach in estimating regional well-being is in line with recent academic literature that studies well-being beyond GDP. Using the OECD Regional

Well-being Dataset, five composite regional well-being indices have been estimated based on an alternative set of weighting schemes for dimensions that assess the substitution level and complementarity between well-being dimensions.

Results show that achievement in the three broad categories of regional well-being and the aggregate regional well-being index changes with the weighting methods employed. The highest values of indices are obtained when dimensions are considered perfect substitutes. The highest achievements are obtained in the personal well-being category, followed by community and material well-being, regardless of the complementarity or substitution between dimensions. It has been shown that regions' position in aggregated regional well-being also changes according to the weighting scheme used for combining the dimensions.

The analysis from 2000 to 2021 shows that, regardless of the weighting method used, changes in the different dimensions of regional well-being produced a worsening in multidimensional well-being from 2000 to 2014, mainly due to a decline in economic activity because of the global financial crisis. Conversely, from 2014 to 2018 and from 2018 to 2021, regional well-being improved, although with different behaviours across the various dimensions of well-being.

Regarding the convergence patterns, different convergence indicators have been estimated, and the dynamic of the distribution has been analysed based on the estimation of stochastic kernels as well as the unconditional beta convergence plots. When the well-being dimensions are considered perfect complements, higher territorial disparities are obtained compared to when these dimensions are considered perfect substitutes. Additionally, the results show a setback in patterns of convergence in regional well-being from 2000 to 2014, while the convergence path may be recovered from 2014 to 2021, determining a convergence pattern in the entire period from 2000 to 2021. However, the weighting methods used for the aggregation of dimensions affect the intensity of the patterns of convergence or divergence.

Therefore, the estimations demonstrate that adopting different weightings yields different results. The selection of dimensions and indicators in constructing a composite well-being index will depend on a particular country's preferences or needs, which is clearly beyond the scope of this study. Nevertheless, policymakers must consider whether the indicators should be treated as complements or substitutes when creating similar indices. The implications of such a decision are undoubtedly relevant, as policies can be misguided and may not lead to genuine improvements in people's well-being.

The results should be taken as an effort to contribute to the debate of convenience about constructing multidimensional regional well-being indices and to raise the relevance of the weighting schemes used for this purpose. It also contributes to updating the results obtained in previous studies, offering the possibility to assess the resilience of EU regions in terms of well-being to face the global economic crisis and the recent health crisis. More in-depth research is needed to understand the dynamics of regional well-being across EU regions. For instance, it is possible to extend the analysis of regional well-being by including two subjective dimensions of well-being, which were excluded in this study as they were not available in 2000. The network support and life satisfaction dimension might be crucial in the aggregate result of the composite index. Furthermore, the analysis of regional well-being and its patterns of convergence could be developed by regional well-being quintiles to shed more light on the differences in outcomes when different weighting schemes are used.

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Appendix

Table 4. Number of regions and countries

Country	Number of regions
Austria	9
Belgium	3
Czech Republic	8
Denmark	5
Estonia	5
Finland	5
France	13
Germany	16
Greece	13
Hungary	7
Ireland	2

Italy	21
Luxembourg	1
Netherlands	12
Poland	16
Portugal	7
Slovak Republic	4
Slovenia	2
Spain	19
Sweden	8
United Kingdom	12
Total	188

Source: Own elaboration based on OECD Regional Well-being Dataset.

Table 5. Regions and countries included in the analysis of EU composite regional well-being index

Country	Region	Country	Region	Country	Region	
Austria	Burgenland	Greece	Attica	Portugal	Alentejo	
	Carinthia		Central Greece		Algarve	
	Lower Austria		Central Macedonia		Azores	
	Salzburg		Crete		Central Portugal	
	Styria		East Macedonia - Thrace		Lisbon	
	Tyrol		Epirus		Madeira	
	Upper Austria		Ionian Islands		North	
	Vienna		North Aegean		Slovak Republic	Bratislava Region
	Vorarlberg		Peloponnese		Central Slovakia	
	Belgium		South Aegean		East Slovakia	
Belgium	Flemish Region (Vlaams Gewest)	Thessaly	West Slovakia	Slovenia	Eastern Slovenia	
	Wallonia (Région wallonne)	West Greece	Western Slovenia			
	Czech Republic	Central Bohemian Region	West Macedonia		Andalusia	
		Central Moravia	Central Hungary		Aragon	
Moravia-Silesia		Central Transdanubia	Asturias			
Northeast		Northern Great Plain	Balearic Islands			
Northwest		Northern Hungary	Basque Country			
Prague		Southern Great Plain	Canary Islands			
Southeast		Southern Transdanubia	Cantabria			
Southwest		Western Transdanubia	Castile and León			
Denmark		Central Jutland	Ireland	Border, Midland and Western	Castile-La Mancha	
		Copenhagen Region	Southern and Eastern	Abruzzo	Catalonia	
	Northern Jutland	Italy	Aosta Valley	Ceuta		
	Southern Denmark	Apulia	Extremadura			
Estonia	Zealand	Basilicata	Galicia			
	Central Estonia	Bolzano-Bozen	La Rioja			
	North Estonia	Calabria	Madrid			
	Northeast Estonia	Campania	Melilla			
Finland	South Estonia	Emilia-Romagna	Murcia			
	West Estonia	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	Navarra			
	Åland	Lazio	Valencia			
	Eastern and Northern Finland	Liguria	Sweden	Central Norrland		
France	Helsinki-Uusimaa	Lombardy	East Middle Sweden			
	Southern Finland	Marche	North Middle Sweden			
	Western Finland	Molise	Småland with Islands			
	Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes	Piedmont	South Sweden			
	Bourgogne-Franche-Comté	Sardinia	Stockholm			
	Brittany	Sicily	Upper Norrland			
	Centre - Val de Loire	Trento	West Sweden			
	Corsica	Tuscany	East Midlands			
	Grand Est	Umbria	East of England			
	Hauts-de-France	Veneto	Greater London			
Germany	Île-de-France	Luxembourg	Luxembourg	North East England		
	Normandy	Netherlands	Drenthe	North West England		
	Nouvelle-Aquitaine	Flevoland	Northern Ireland			
	Occitanie	Friesland	Scotland			
	Pays de la Loire	Gelderland	South East England			
	Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur	Groningen	South West England			
	Baden-Württemberg	Limburg	Wales			
	Bavaria	North Brabant	West Midlands			
	Berlin	North Holland	Yorkshire and The Humber			
	Brandenburg	Overijssel				
Bremen	South Holland					
Germany	Hamburg	Utrecht				
	Hesse	Zeeland				
	Lower Saxony	Poland	Dolnoslaskie			
	Mecklenburg-Vorpommern	Kujawsko-Pomorskie				
	North Rhine-Westphalia	Lódzkie				
	Rhineland-Palatinate	Lubelskie				
	Saarland	Lubuskie				
	Saxony	Malopolskie				
	Saxony-Anhalt	Mazowieckie				
	Schleswig-Holstein	Opolskie				
Thuringia	Podkarpackie					
	Podlaskie					
	Pomorskie					
	Slaskie					
	Swietokrzyskie					
	Warminsko-Mazurskie					
	Wielkopolskie					
	Zachodniopomorskie					

Source: Own elaboration based on OECD Regional Well-being Dataset.

Table 6. Composite regional well-being index. Top-15 EU regions, 2021

N°	Region	Country	WBI_1	N°	Region	Country	WBI_2	N°	Region	Country	WBI_3
1	Luxembourg	Luxembourg	0,863	1	Luxembourg	Luxembourg	0,855	1	Luxembourg	Luxembourg	0,847
2	Central Norrland	Sweden	0,834	2	Central Norrland	Sweden	0,829	2	Central Norrland	Sweden	0,823
3	Drenthe	Netherlands	0,829	3	Schleswig-Holstein	Germany	0,820	3	Schleswig-Holstein	Germany	0,817
4	South East England	United Kingdom	0,827	4	South East England	United Kingdom	0,819	4	Småland with Islands	Sweden	0,810
5	Småland with Islands	Sweden	0,825	5	Drenthe	Netherlands	0,819	5	South East England	United Kingdom	0,810
6	Flemish Region (Vlaams Gewest)	Belgium	0,824	6	Småland with Islands	Sweden	0,818	6	Baden-Württemberg	Germany	0,809
7	Zeeland	Netherlands	0,823	7	South West England	United Kingdom	0,816	7	South West England	United Kingdom	0,809
8	Bavaria	Germany	0,823	8	Bavaria	Germany	0,815	8	Drenthe	Netherlands	0,807
9	Schleswig-Holstein	Germany	0,823	9	Baden-Württemberg	Germany	0,814	9	West Sweden	Sweden	0,807
10	South West England	United Kingdom	0,823	10	Upper Norrland	Sweden	0,813	10	Bavaria	Germany	0,806
11	North Brabant	Netherlands	0,821	11	West Sweden	Sweden	0,813	11	Rhineland-Palatinate	Germany	0,805
12	Upper Norrland	Sweden	0,821	12	Flemish Region (Vlaams Gewest)	Belgium	0,812	12	Upper Norrland	Sweden	0,805
13	Utrecht	Netherlands	0,820	13	Zeeland	Netherlands	0,811	13	East Middle Sweden	Sweden	0,804
14	Baden-Württemberg	Germany	0,819	14	Lower Austria	Austria	0,811	14	Southern Finland	Finland	0,803
15	Lower Austria	Austria	0,819	15	Southern Finland	Finland	0,810	15	Helsinki-Uusimaa	Finland	0,801

...(cont).

N°	Region	Country	WBI_4	N°	Region	Country	WBI_5
1	Luxembourg	Luxembourg	0,972	1	Luxembourg	Luxembourg	0,963
2	Småland with Islands	Sweden	0,939	2	Central Norrland	Sweden	0,932
3	Central Norrland	Sweden	0,939	3	Småland with Islands	Sweden	0,931
4	West Sweden	Sweden	0,933	4	West Sweden	Sweden	0,926
5	Southern Finland	Finland	0,930	5	East Middle Sweden	Sweden	0,923
6	East Middle Sweden	Sweden	0,930	6	Southern Finland	Finland	0,923
7	South East England	United Kingdom	0,929	7	Helsinki-Uusimaa	Finland	0,920
8	Drenthe	Netherlands	0,928	8	South East England	United Kingdom	0,920
9	Helsinki-Uusimaa	Finland	0,927	9	Stockholm	Sweden	0,919
10	South West England	United Kingdom	0,927	10	South West England	United Kingdom	0,919
11	Stockholm	Sweden	0,927	11	Drenthe	Netherlands	0,918
12	Western Finland	Finland	0,926	12	Western Finland	Finland	0,917
13	Upper Norrland	Sweden	0,924	13	Upper Norrland	Sweden	0,915
14	Greater London	United Kingdom	0,922	14	Schleswig-Holstein	Germany	0,914
15	Bavaria	Germany	0,922	15	Lower Austria	Austria	0,913

Source: Own elaboration based on OECD Regional Well-being Dataset.

Figure 5. Kernel estimation of regional well-being index density function, 2000, 2014, 2018 y 2021

Source: Own elaboration based on OECD Regional Well-being Dataset.